

KATE BAGNALL

FROM HONG KONG TO SYDNEY: THE JOURNEY OF THE GLAMIS CASTLE, 1881

'ALL ROADS LEAD TO HONG KONG': PEOPLE, CITY, EMPIRES
HONG KONG HISTORY PROJECT CONFERENCE
6-7 JUNE 2019, UNIVERSITY OF HONG KONG

In a fortnight
2000
Chinese
large numbers
to follow
from
Hongkong

PUNCH'S PROTEST.

Mr. Punch to Sir Henry Parkes: "REALLY, SIR HENRY, THIS INFLUX OF CHINESE MUST BE STOPPED."
Sir Henry Parkes: "BUT THE 'OUSE IS HUP YOU KNOW, MY DEAR FELLOW."
Mr. Punch: "BUT MR, NO BUTS. THIS MUST BE STOPPED, AND AT ONCE."

'PUNCH'S PROTEST'

Sydney Punch, 23 April 1881, p. 5

Mr Punch to Sir Henry Parkes [Premier of New South Wales]:

'Really, Sir Henry, the influx of Chinese must be stopped.'

Sir Henry Parkes: 'But the 'ouse is hup you know, my dear fellow.'

Mr Punch: 'But me, no buts. This must be stopped, and at once.'

<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article253062090>

Thomas Ham & Co., 'Map shewing position of Queensland to the Australian colonies, India, China, &c.', 1865
<http://nla.gov.au/nla.obj-230996378>

'CHINESE LIFE IN SYDNEY'

Illustrated Sydney News, 12 June 1880, p. 13

1. New arrivals to Circular Quay
2. Chair-making in George Street
3. Gardening at Botany
4. Chinese vegetable seller
5. Police raid on a Chinese gambling den in Goulburn Street

<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article64973572>

Year	Immigrants	Emigrants
1859	3,022	450
1860	6,958	1,098
1861	2,574	893
1862	1,030	1,118
1863	633
1864	1,044
1865	832
1866	913
1867	852
1868	123	548
1869	288	574
1870	30	525
1871	426	463
1872	229	597
1873	406	400
1874	865	933
1875	625	1,209
1876	696	940
1877	884	490
1878	2,485	1,560
1879	1,979	557
1880	2,942	876
1881	4,465	929
1882	1,007	884
1883	1,936	1,402
1884	2,191	1,038
1885	2,929	1,726
1886	3,092	1,883
1887	4,436	2,773
1888 ¹²	1,848	1,562
1889	7	941

CHINESE MIGRATION TO NEW SOUTH WALES

1861 NSW Chinese Immigrants Regulation
and Restriction Act

1867 NSW Repeal of 1861 Chinese Immigrants Act

1877 QLD Chinese Immigrants Regulation Act

1881 NSW Influx of Chinese Restriction Act

1888 NSW Chinese Restriction and Regulation Act

CHINESE ARRIVALS IN SYDNEY, JANUARY TO APRIL 1881

Report by Edmund Fosbery, Inspector General of Police, for the Colonial Secretary, 22 April 1881

Date	Ship	No. of Chinese Passengers
13 January	Menmuir	84
24 January	Brisbane	177
5 February	Meath	77
19 February	Bowen	86
4 April	Menmuir	645
8 April	Hungarian	479
16 April	Kenmure Castle	656
		TOTAL = 2204

NSW State Archives, NRS 906: Colonial Secretary, Special Bundles,
'Proposed prohibition of Chinese Immigration into Australia', 4/829.1

We have been making further inquiries regarding the cause of the great influx of Chinese which has been taking place during the past two or three weeks. It appears that of the large number—over 2000—of Chinese who have lately arrived, fully 1400 or 1600 have left Sydney for the interior, and have scattered themselves wherever there is a chance of their finding employment. This chance seems to exist principally on the New England tin mines, and thither most of the new arrivals have gone. The tin mines are worked chiefly by Chinamen—who are engaged by

certain of their number and known by the name of the system of working on tribute. By this means much below what it would be to miners, and in fact the proprietors. The tin-mining work for a saved a little money—somewhere else, or, it may be engaged by the “Bo” those whose terms of service these contracting Chinese labourers, and in other from here to their relations them to come to the colony been exactly the cause of here, but from inquiries that the good accounts of the opportunities for making had a great deal to do Sydney. February and when emigration from than at any other period coupled with the circum-

tion received in China or the labour market in New South Wales—are attributed the recent shipments. There is no information to show that the arrival of the Chinamen is the result of speculation on the part of anybody or that it is under Chinese official sanction. There are remaining in Sydney now about 400 of the new arrivals, distributed among the various Chinese lodging-houses, and in a few days most of those will, it is believed, leave for the interior. The majority of them will proceed to the tin mines and others will go on the gold-fields, or employ themselves in the occupation of hawkers or market gardeners. They are all said to be a class of labourers superior in outward appearance to those generally seen here. Certainly the remnant of them now in Sydney are, on the whole, a strong muscular set of men. This is believed to be due to the circumstance that when in China they did not belong to the population of any of the towns, and were not addicted to Chinese vices, such as opium smoking and drinking. They are nearly all represented to be farmers or agriculturists, and they have come from the districts of Koo You, Poon Yee, Heong Sang, See Yip, Tong Gong, and Tching Singh, which are around Canton and Hongkong. Most of the men have some money, and all are said to have paid their passages by the steamers which brought them here. This passage money amounted in each case to 43 dollars or £9, without provisions, the Chinese supplying themselves with food during the voyage, and those whose passage stripped them of all or most of the money they possessed, are being assisted by their relatives or friends in this colony. Tin War and Co., Chinese merchants in Sydney, received, at the instance of the friends of

FOR THE REST OF THEIR LIVES.

We are informed by the Colonial Secretary that he has already telegraphed to the British authorities in China for information as to the reasons for this invasion, which, in the present state of the law, the Government are utterly powerless to prevent. It will, perhaps, be remembered that the present Government, soon after they took office, introduced a bill to deal with the question of Chinese immigration. That bill they succeeded in carrying through the Legislative Assembly by large majorities, but it was thrown out in the Legislative Council on the second reading. It may also be recollected that the orators who are in the habit

‘Chinese immigration’, *Sydney Morning Herald*, 22 April 1881, p. 6

<http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article13479631>

81-6014

No 1161.

Colonial Secretary's Office
Hong Kong, 22nd June, 1881 -

Sir,

1. Having laid before Governor Sir John Pope Hennessy your telegram of the 20th of April, I was directed by His Excellency to telegraph in reply, that the information you required would be transmitted to you, and that His Excellency's Government was carefully watching the Chinese Emigration to Australia.

2. You wish to know under what auspices the Chinese Emigrants are leaving China for Australia. An answer to that

Put by for present 15-6-81

The Honourable
The Colonial Secretary
Sydney
New South Wales.

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GOVERNMENT NOTIFICATION.—No. 256.

The following despatch and enclosures are published for general information.

By His Excellency's Command,

FREDERICK STEWART,
Acting Colonial Secretary.

Colonial Secretary's Office, Hongkong, 23rd July, 1881.

No. 1161.

COLONIAL SECRETARY'S OFFICE,
HONGKONG, 22nd June, 1881.

SIR,—Having laid before Governor Sir JOHN POPE HENNESSY your telegram of the 20th of April, I was directed by His Excellency to telegraph in reply, that the information you required would be transmitted to you, and that His Excellency's Government was carefully watching the Chinese Emigration to Australia.

2. You wish to know under what auspices the Chinese Emigrants are leaving China for Australia. An answer to that question is to some extent furnished by the printed papers I have the honour to transmit herewith, relating to the Chinese Emigrants that went to Sydney and other Australian ports in the *Glamis Castle*.

3. Before signing the licence, the Governor called for an independent examination in addition to the statutory examination of the Emigration Officer. You will observe that the examination of a few of the proposed Emigrants by Dr. EITEL, the Acting Chinese Secretary, was a very searching one. The Governor is of opinion that the facts elicited by Dr. EITEL, as well as those obtained by the Acting Registrar General and myself, may be taken as applying generally to the class of Chinese Emigrants proceeding from Hongkong to Australia.

4. His Excellency desires me to enclose, for your information, a copy of the local Ordinances which, with the Imperial Act 18 and 19 Vic., Cap. 104, prescribe and limit the Governor's powers in this matter of Chinese Emigration. The printed papers relating to the case of the *Glamis Castle* will enable you to see how the Emigration Ordinances are worked. The enclosed correspondence of the year 1878 relating to the S. S. *Mecca*, and of 1880 relating to the S. S. *Meath*, may also be of interest to the New South Wales Government.*

5. I have the honour to enclose a list of the steamers that left this Colony for Australia with Chinese Emigrants or passengers since the 1st of January this year, and a list of those at present announced to sail for Sydney.

I have, &c.,

FREDERICK STEWART,
Acting Colonial Secretary.

The Honourable
THE COLONIAL SECRETARY,
SYDNEY,
New South Wales.

* Some of these papers have been published in the *Government Gazette*, Nos. 32 and 38 of 1880, and No. 18 of 1881.

PASSENGERS DEPARTING HONG KONG FOR AUSTRALIAN COLONIES,
1 JANUARY TO 22 JUNE 1881

Destination	Men	Women	Boys	Girls	Total
Port Darwin	62	—	2	—	64
Cooktown	65	—	1	—	66
Cleveland Bay [Townsville]	3	—	—	—	3
Brisbane	2	—	—	—	2
Sydney	3600	—	37	—	3637
Melbourne	427	—	8	—	435
	4259	—	48	—	4207

NSW State Archives, NRS 905: Main series of letters received [Colonial Secretary],
'Reports re Chinese emigration', 81/6014 [1/2512]

AGE OF PASSENGERS ON THE GLAMIS CASTLE, APRIL 1881

District of origin of passengers on the *Glamis Castle*, April 1881. Not shown: SUI SHIN, KWONG SHEN, HEONG SHOW

DISTRICT OF ORIGIN OF PASSENGERS ON THE GLAMIS CASTLE, APRIL 1881

DESTINATIONS OF PASSENGERS ON THE GLAMIS CASTLE, APRIL 1881

OCCUPATIONS OF PASSENGERS ON THE GLAMIS CASTLE, APRIL 1881

'I am going to Sydney. I am a carpenter. My uncle is a carpenter in Sydney. I am going to my uncle. My father paid my passage. It is my wish to go. I know I can do what I like, and go where I like. My father's name is LAU-KI. He lived in the Ú-cheung shop in Chung-wán. My father is not here with me just now, but my uncle is. He is going with me. I have not been enticed in any way. I shall have to pay nothing back for my passage. I expect \$7 a month. I have had no wages hitherto. I have been an apprentice.'

– LAU A'IN (LAW YIN), 12 YEARS OLD, 'GOLD DIGGER', NO. 276

'I am 35 years of age. I am going to Sydney. I come from Lung-to in Héung-shán. I have paid \$42 for my passage. I pay it myself. I saved the money. I was once in Sydney before. I returned the year before last. I was 4 years there. I brought back \$300. I have given it to my wife. I have 3 children. I got my ticket at the Wo-tsán in Wo Hing Lane, Shéung-wán. I have been 4 or 5 days in the house. There are 24 or 25 of us there. I speak some English. I shall have nothing to pay for my passage.'

– LAU A-FAI (LAW FA), 'GOLD DIGGER', NO. 275

A CHINESE CAMP AND JOSS HOUSE AT VEGETABLE CREEK

Chinese camp and joss house at Vegetable Creek (Emmaville), NSW

Illustrated Sydney News, 3 September 1881, p. 13, <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article64974561>

INFLUX OF CHINESE RESTRICTION ACT OF 1881 (45 VIC NO 11) (NSW)

- applied to 'any person of the Chinese race'
- £10 poll tax on each Chinese arriving by sea or land
- entry of Chinese by sea limited to one person for every 100 tons of shipping
- penalties could apply to ships' masters and to Chinese passengers
- exemptions for British subjects, 'bona fide' residents of NSW, Chinese government officials, crew

Repealed Official Copy

This PUBLIC BILL originated in the LEGISLATIVE ASSEMBLY, and, having this day passed, is now ready for presentation to the LEGISLATIVE COUNCIL for its concurrence.

*Legislative Assembly Chamber,
Sydney, 17 May, 1888, A.M. }*

*F. W. WEBB,
Clerk of Legislative Assembly.*

New South Wales.

ANNO QUINQUAGESIMO PRIMO

VICTORIÆ REGINÆ.

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No. .

An Act to repeal the "Influx of Chinese Restriction Act of 1881"; to provide for the protection of the Colony from the disturbances and national dangers of Chinese immigration; to provide specially for the regulation of Chinese at present resident within the Colony; and to indemnify the Government for all acts done by Executive or Ministerial authority in relation to Chinese immigrants, or vessels carrying such immigrants, since the first day of May, one thousand eight hundred and eighty-eight.

WHEREAS it is expedient to provide for the protection of the Colony of New South Wales from the disturbances and national dangers which may arise from the influx of Chinese under restrictions hitherto existing, and also to provide for the regulation of Chinese resident within the said Colony: And whereas it is just and expedient to indemnify the Executive Government for all acts done by any member thereof in relation to Chinese immigrants, or any ship carrying such immigrants, since the first day of May, one thousand eight hundred and eighty-eight: Be it therefore enacted by the Queen's Most Excellent Majesty, by and with the advice and consent of the Legislative Council and Legislative Assembly of New South Wales in Parliament assembled, and by the authority of the same, as follows:—

1. The Act, entitled "*An Act to restrict the Influx of Chinese* Repeal of 45 Vic., into *New South Wales*," forty-fifth Victoria number eleven, is hereby No. 11. repealed. But the repeal hereby enacted shall not affect the past operation 784—A

CHINESE MIGRATION TO NEW SOUTH WALES

TABLE VII.—CHINESE¹¹ IMMIGRATION AND EMIGRATION, 1859-1919.

Year	Immigrants	Emigrants	Year	Immigrants	Emigrants
1859	3,022	450	1890	15	637
1860	6,958	1,098	1891	17	581
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1862	1,030	1,118	1893	34	558
1863	633	1894	76	627
1864	1,044	1895	94	413
1865	832	1896	99	450
1866	913	1897	34	428
1867	852	1898	32	419
1868	123	548	1899	36	449
1869	288	574	1900	75	379
1870	30	525	1901	71	342
1871	426	463	1902	56	425
1872	229	597	1903	62	676
1873	406	400	1904	176	702
1874	865	933	1905	392	948
1875	625	1,209	1906	364	818
1876	696	940	1907	375	928
1877	884	490	1908	497	883
1878	2,485	1,560	1909	562	900
1879	1,979	557	1910	502	807
1880	2,942	876	1911	753	844
1881	4,465	929	1912	887	1,052
1882	1,007	884	1913	1,000	1,131
1883	1,936	1,402	1914	957	1,096
1884	2,191	1,038	1915	1,135	1,235
1885	2,929	1,726	1916	1,141	1,203
1886	3,092	1,883	1917	923	797
1887	4,436	2,773	1918	883	704
1888 ¹²	1,848	1,562	1919	786	791
1889	7	941

Walter F. Willcox, *International Migrations, Volume I: Statistics*
 (National Bureau of Economic Research, 1929) <https://www.nber.org/chapters/c5146>

PASSENGERS BY A CHINA TEA STEAMER.

Passengers by the S.S. Ocean, a China tea steamer, Sandridge, Melbourne, July 1881
Illustrated Australian News, 27 July 1881, p. 133 (and article p. 138)
<http://handle.slv.vic.gov.au/10381/132520>; <http://nla.gov.au/nla.news-article63185668>